

STIMULATION OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY IN YOUNG SCHOOLCHILDREN AND ITS PSYCHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Development of cognitive activity of students of primary school age is one of the urgent problems in modern education. This article describes the tasks of the school psychologist in the development of the knowledge of primary school students, the formation of cognitive educational activity in increasing the effectiveness of education and its stimulation, and the theoretical basis of the technology of cognitive activity.

Cognitive activity is a conscious activity aimed at knowing the surrounding reality with the help of mental processes such as perception, thinking, memory, attention, speech. Cognitive activity is the activity of mastering knowledge and action methods and self-development in the process of solving educational problems set by the teacher. It is aimed not only at mastering knowledge and skills, but also at improving and developing personal qualities of the subject (student) due to the purposeful assimilation of social experience (moral, cultural, practical, creative, etc.).

From this point of view, the cognitive activity of primary school students in the educational process includes three interrelated stages:

1. At the first stage, perception, understanding and memorization of the studied material or assimilation of theoretical knowledge takes place.
2. At the second stage, skills and abilities to apply this knowledge are developed, which requires the organization of special training exercises.
3. In the third stage, further strengthening and deepening of knowledge on the studied material, their integration and improvement of practical skills and qualifications are carried out.

The problem of the development of cognitive activity is one of the most urgent issues in the psychology of children, because the interaction of a person with the outside world can be realized thanks to his activity. Activity is an indispensable condition for the formation of intellectual qualities of a person, his independence and initiative.

Cognitive activity as a pedagogical phenomenon is a two-way interrelated process: on the one hand, cognitive activity is a form of student self-organization and self-awareness; on the

other hand, cognitive activity is considered as the result of the teacher's special actions in organizing the student's cognitive activity.

Therefore, when defining cognitive activity, we need to have an idea of what type or aspect of cognitive activity we are talking about. At the same time, we must not forget that the final result of the teacher's efforts is to turn the specially organized activity of the student into an independent activity, a process of self-education. Thus, both types of cognitive activity are closely related to each other.

In a number of studies, the problem of studying cognitive activity was considered in the context of creativity.

F. Kharlamov interpreted cognitive activity as "the student's active state characterized by the desire to learn, mental stress and the manifestation of voluntary actions in the process of acquiring knowledge."

I. Shchukina considered cognitive activity "representing the unique state of the student and his attitude to the activity", "valuable and complex personal education of the student, which is intensively formed during the school years."

Kabanova-Meller considers the system of forming generalized methods of educational work, which are important components of effective educational activity of students in the development of cognitive activity.

Cognitive activity methods - creative use of mental work methods that ensure the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities, their independent application and active change, productive independent work skills, help in the formation of generalized educational skills will give.

In our opinion, these concepts should be distinguished from each other, because the term "mental activity" describes a certain level of mastering more mental operations and is the result of cognitive activity. As for "cognitive activity", it is incomplete and includes the process of acquiring knowledge.

Interests serve as a psychological condition of the child's need to acquire theoretical knowledge. In the process of formation of the need for educational activities among schoolchildren of a young age, it is concretized in various motives, which requires children to behave. Implementation of this method of assimilation implies special activation of cognitive activity. It is based on changing the educational material, introducing the student to the origin of knowledge by highlighting the most fundamental, basic concepts.

Cognitive activity, like any personal characteristic and motivation of the student's activity, develops and is formed in the activity and, first of all, in teaching. Fundamental researches in the field of education of young students reveal the process of formation of cognitive activity of elementary school students and define changes in educational content, generalized methods of educational activity and formation of logical thinking methods.

The formation of students' cognitive activity in learning can be realized through two main channels, on the one hand, if this possibility is embodied in the content of academic subjects, on the other hand, through a specific organization of students' cognitive activity. . The first thing that is a subject of cognitive interest for schoolchildren is the acquisition of new knowledge about the world. That is why it is the most important part of choosing the content of the

educational material, showing the wealth of scientific knowledge, and forming interest in learning.

It is known that early school age is the period of formation and development of the most general abilities, which improve and develop as the child grows up. One of the most important skills is the ability to know.

The process of primary education is aimed at the development of cognitive abilities and their implementation in children aged 7-11. Interaction with the child should be organized in such a way that it should be aimed at forming cognitive interest, cognitive independence and initiative.

The main forms of interaction that contribute to cognitive development:

Involve the child in various activities;

Use of didactic games;

It consists in the use of teaching methods aimed at enriching the development of creative imagination, thinking, memory, and speech.

It is important for teachers who organize the learning process to know the structure of the activity. Its main components are: motives, purpose, tasks, content, means, forms, methods and result. So, the teacher should influence the emotional-motivational, mental, and practical spheres of the students' personality with the help of various means. It is also important for teachers to know the main types of activities in which schoolchildren participate. They are as follows; educational-cognitive, social, work, play, aesthetic, sports and recreation. Interlinking these activities is very important. The primary school teacher is largely the organizer of students' cognitive independent activity. Cognitive education is currently achieved through alternative programs, differentiated methods, creative homework, extracurricular forms of student activity organization. Modern studies of psychologists on cognitive education convincingly prove that the cognitive activity of students when solving research problems differs from solving standardized problems.

Cognitive activity reflects the constant need of young students to use new knowledge, skills, internal purposefulness and various methods of action to supplement knowledge, expand knowledge and expand their horizons.

In conclusion, it can be said that cognitive activity is an important activity that determines the student's own position, willingness to learn and desire to gain a new position in society. In educational activities, the child works with scientific concepts under the guidance of the teacher, learns them. As a result, changes occur in the student himself, in his development. Formation of cognitive educational activity of elementary school students, development of interests, education of active attitude to work, first of all, takes place in class. The student works with interest in the lesson. For this, at every stage of any lesson, it is necessary to activate students' cognitive activity and increase interest in learning, use different methods, forms and types of work and encourage it.

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